

RESULTS OF THE DoD LIVEWARE SURVEY

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ABSTRACT

How can the United States (US) military achieve more with the people resources it will have after the current downsizing efforts are complete? One way is to improve the human-machine relationship. To achieve this goal, the DoD has mandated a series of Human Systems Integration (HSI) analyses throughout the defense acquisition process. Now Government and contractor employees alike must find the HSI technologies that can help achieve better consideration of human issues during acquisition and better integration of the human into each defense system developed or modified. Recently, there has been an explosion of affordable HSI technologies. Despite the new DoD directives that require HSI analyses throughout acquisition, it is very difficult to identify the most appropriate technology for HSI analyses. Defense acquisition managers, their contractors, and the HSI research and development community need a database of information about HSI tools, databases, and test facilities. They need this information to easily identify technology available in each of the Liveware domains of Manpower, Personnel, Training (MPT), Safety, Health Hazard Prevention, and Human Factors Engineering (HFE) to fully integrate human consideration into the acquisition process. However, no comprehensive catalog of HSI technology exists. Under the sponsorship of the Office of the Assistant Secretary of Defense (Force Management and Personnel) HSI office and North Atlantic Treaty Organization (NATO) Research Study Group.21 (RSG.21), ARL-HRED-STRICOM and CSERIAC have surveyed the HSI community to obtain a comprehensive database of HSI technologies. Highlights of the survey and resulting database are presented

below. After background information, this paper discusses the methods used to collect information about the HSI technologies, findings, and implications of the Liveware survey.

BACKGROUND

Importance of HSI in Defense Acquisitions

The US and NATO militaries are all downsizing during the post-Cold War era, while some other nations are taking advantage of inexpensive military hardware and expertise to expand their military capability. Economic pressures to spend less on military preparation increase, while the number of tyrants and ethnic conflicts increase. In addition, US equipment and training must be targeted for the kinds of skirmishes and wars we are likely to fight in the future. We are all caught up in a period of change. The question of how to be more prepared with fewer people constantly raises the need for better ways to include HSI issues and technologies in the Defense materiel acquisition process.

DoD Directives Contain HSI Requirements

Recognizing the need for more effective human-materiel inter-relationships, the DoD defense systems acquisition directives (DoDD 5000.1, DoDI 5000.2, and DoD 5000.2M) document a series of HSI analyses and data to be furnished throughout the Defense acquisition process. Pressures to accomplish more with smaller defense forces, and the widening interest and direction in HSI as a means to this end, have accelerated the need for comprehensive information about available HSI tools, databases, and test facilities. Department of Defense

Instruction (DoDI) 5000.2, *Defense Acquisition Management Policies and Procedures*, requires the effective integration of human considerations in the design effort to improve total system performance and reduce life-cycle cost. Objectives for the human components of a system are to be established at Milestone I, and addressed, refined, and updated throughout acquisition. This DoDI requires that appropriate HSI studies, analyses, plans, and milestone issues be addressed at each phase of the Defense acquisition process.

Need for Available HSI Technologies

To meet the challenge of these changing times and the requirements of directives, Defense acquisition personnel and their contractors require access to a set of proven HSI technologies readily available to use during acquisition. Acquisition and system development personnel need tools, data, and methods of influencing design for increased human efficiency, safety, and to minimize hazards. These technologies are so important that "human-system interfaces" and "design automation" that includes representation of people-related issues, and "environmental effects" are 3 of the top 11 DoD key technologies listed by the Director of Defense Research and Engineering (1992, July). The goal of these technologies is to help the person perform more effectively under all stressor conditions so that fewer of "our" people than "their" people are needed to do the job. In other words, our people must be prepared to do more with fewer people, while remaining more protected from "harm's way." HSI technologies exist for just that reason; yet sometimes there seems to be a disconnect between the developer of HSI technology and the potential user. For this reason, OASD(FM&P) HSI Office undertook the DoD Liveware survey in conjunction with other NATO member countries. The goal is to take stock of HSI technologies and index them so that information about these technologies will be easily found.

NATO RSG.21

Likewise across NATO, other nations are awakening to similar needs. Member countries have found HSI processes to be a means of ensuring effective development/modification of defense systems. NATO Defense Research Group Panel 8, *Defense Applications of Human and Bio-medical Sciences*, established Research Study Group 21 (RSG.21). This group, designated *Liveware Integration in Weapon System Acquisition*,

was chartered to study how the human-machine interface was addressed and how human-related issues were resolved during acquisition by member nations. Participant nations are listed in Figure 1.

Figure 1

RSG.21 is chaired by Mr. Michael Pearce of the Office of the Assistant Secretary of Defense (OASD), Force Management and Personnel (FM&P)/Requirements and Resources (R&R), Total Force Requirements (TFR), HSI office.

Liveware Defined

As RSG.21 wrestled with the difficulty in communicating concepts like Army MANPRINT, Navy HARDMAN, and Air Force IMPACTS -- acronyms for programs that implement HSI in US Services -- they coined a new term, "Liveware," which seemed to make sense across the national boundaries and languages.

Figure 2

Liveware collectively describes all acquisition disciplines which directly affect humans in defense systems. Liveware domains include MPT, Safety, Health Hazard Prevention, and HFE, the same disciplines involved in HSI. Figure 2 displays the logo which symbolizes the Liveware concept of six domains integrated in an atom structure, the center of which is the human. The biomechanical humanoid mannequin is used to symbolize the computer-aided design technology which allows integration of human issues into design engineers' workplaces, while in the midst of their creative activity.

Tasking

RSG.21 was tasked to identify, define, and describe the tools, techniques, and databases that enhance early consideration and integration of human issues into the total system; evaluate these findings; and identify gaps and voids for future research and development (R&D) efforts. Moving to meet this NATO-wide need, the OASD(FM&P) HSI Office tasked the Defense Training and Performance Data Center (TPDC) to develop a comprehensive database of "Liveware" information.

Project Overview and Implementers

TPDC Started Project. To build the Liveware database, TPDC developed the survey instrument to collect essential information from HSI technology developers, owners, and users. Liveware survey questions were reviewed and approved by RSG.21 members. Since this involved translating across service, nation, language, and scientific discipline, developing a consensus on the questions was no small challenge. Each country was to survey its own HSI community and share the results with TPDC, which would place the results in the Liveware database.

ARL-HRED-STRICOM. Shortly after initiating the Liveware survey, TPDC was disestablished under DoD downsizing. As TPDC closed its doors, the Liveware project manager, Dr. Mona Crissey, moved to the Army Research Lab's Human Research and Engineering Directorate field element at US Army STRICOM, also in Orlando, Florida, where she continued to direct the Liveware project.

CSERIAC. CSERIAC was requested to assist with publicity, make contact with human system integration and human factors Points of Contact (POCs), and to refine, verify, and analyze the survey information as subject matter experts in the area of Human Factors and Human System Integration.

Liveware Project Goals

The specific goal of the Liveware survey is to be the most comprehensive study of HSI technology yet accomplished. It will document tools, databases, methods, and facilities in all Liveware domains. The Liveware database will be available on-line and on disk to the Government and Industry acquisition communities. This database will support effective use of HSI tools and databases throughout the acquisition process. In addition, it will store the results furnished by other NATO nations collected from their internal surveys. Liveware database analyses will help identify HSI technology gaps and set the research agenda to improve these technologies. The overall goal is to help DoD and NATO member nation acquisition personnel and their contractors identify and use HSI technologies, to ultimately provide the most cost-effective defense systems possible.

Previous Studies/Background Search

Previous Studies. CSERIAC performed a background/literature search to determine the extent to which this information had been studied before. Nine studies were identified (and described in last year's NAECON paper [Gentner & Crissey, 1992, May]) that covered parts of the Liveware domains. Two were conducted by the US Army Human Engineering Lab (USAHEL) which focused primarily on human engineering and Army tools. The first (Fleger et al, 1988) established a high standard, though limited to one HSI domain. The second is contained in the USAHEL program IDEA currently in progress. The Air Force Human Systems Division (HSD) and Aeronautical Systems Division (ASD) MPT Directorate (ASD/ALH) were involved with two efforts to identify Air Force tools and databases. A unique aspect of the HSD (Rossmeyssl et al, 1990) study was that it linked each tool to acquisition decisions which it could help support. The ASD/ALH study (Gentner, 1991) added Air Force safety and health hazard databases and tools which were missing from the HSD effort. A major descriptive effort was undertaken by the DoD HFE Technical Group to categorize design support methods (Bogner et al, 1990). It also includes military standards, regulations, and MANPRINT process guides. This study, which focuses on Army manpower, personnel, and human factors engineering technologies and procedures, is available from the Manpower and Training Research Information System (MATRIS). The Logistics Support Analysis Techniques Guide (AMC Pamphlet 700-4) lightly covers

maintainer MPT along with other logistics areas. Two Computer-Aided Acquisition and Logistics Support (CALs)-related studies were conducted under the auspices of the CALs Human System Components committee. They cover only automated tools in manpower and personnel (Bravo and Bakalarski, 1991), and in training development (Wall, 1991, and Wall and Tucker, 1990) domains, respectively. A Canadian summary paper (Beevis, 1991) highlighted a few unique Canadian tools, and indicated that they rely on many US Service-developed tools.

None Comprehensive. These studies were not comprehensive. (See Gentner and Crissey [1992, Oct] for a table depicting gaps and areas of coverage.) In discussions with several of the authors of previous efforts, several factors limited the scope of their studies: (1) the study was planned to cover only one or a few domains or Service components; (2) the breadth of the study was limited by funding or expertise; (3) participation from all domains and Services was not forthcoming and/or time was not available to prod tool developers into submitting input; and (4) the organizational infrastructure and technology did not exist within the Services (especially in the case of health hazards prevention).

Technologies Difficult to Find. In addition to the lack of a comprehensive review and analysis of HSI technology, these technologies are not easily found in the professional literature. While many technical references to many of these technologies do exist, Liveware technologies are not easy to find in existing technical reference databases. Often multiple cross-references are needed to find one single technology, even if one knows the technology. This dearth of easily accessible information on HSI technologies reinforces the need for a "living" Liveware database.

METHOD

Survey Content

Survey questions are divided into three sections: General Program Information, Descriptive Information, and Owner/User Information. The data elements available from the Liveware database are listed below:

General Program Information. Section I is divided into ten major areas. Program Identification captures the program name, acronym, description, type of

technology, country of origin, community sector, state of development, availability, accessibility, and portability. The Purpose and Acquisition Phase covers mission area, system area, system and force level, and acquisition phase. The next three areas cover Hardware Requirements, Software Requirements, and Linkages to other tools/databases. Documentation captures the names and dates of the technical reference and user instruction documents, data output mode, and availability of data field descriptions and data record layout. The Validity area has product validation information. The three final areas are text fields covering Assumptions, Limitations, and Remarks.

Descriptive Information. Section II identifies the Liveware domains addressed by the program, applicable categories within each domain, and environmental areas of concern to safety and health hazard programs. Also, if the technology integrates several domains, the method of integration (vertical and/or horizontal) is specified.

Owner/User Information. Section III covers multiple areas. The owning organization, POC, and multiple users are identified. For each POC, the following information is collected: organization name, address and telephone number; user work discipline; domains applied; and frequency of use. (For a detailed description of the survey see Gentner & Crissey, 1992, May).

Survey Administration Strategy

Publicity. Maximum publicity was sought by publishing papers/articles and presenting them in professional forums and publications, such as the National Aerospace and Electronics Conference (NAECON), Human Factors Society, Interservice/Industry Training Systems and Education Conference (IITSEC), DoD Human Factors Engineering Technical Group (DoD HFE TG), CSERIAC *Gateway*, and other conference/workshop proceedings.

Literature searches. CSERIAC conducted a series of specialized literature searches and technical references to identify potential technology POCs, who were sent Liveware surveys.

Follow-up and Networking. CSERIAC followed-up by phone on surveys not returned within several months. Phone, electronic mail, and facsimile calls also served to use "networking" techniques to identify other technologies and POCs.

Literature entries. When POCs did not respond, available literature was used to develop survey data. When possible, those literature entries were coordinated with the POC.

Table 1
LIVEWARE SURVEY PARTICIPATION
BY SERVICE/INDUSTRY (As of February 3, 1993)

LIVEWARE DOMAIN	UNITED STATES						TOTAL BY DOMAIN
	AIR FORCE	ARMY	NAVY/MARINES	OTHER GOV'T	INDUSTRY	UNIVERSITIES/ OTHERS	
MANPOWER	44	28	8	6	46	10	142
PERSONNEL	36	29	5	6	43	14	133
TRAINING	55	39	24	14	69	26	227
SAFETY	27	11	7	2	31	4	82
HEALTH HAZARDS	20	12	5	0	22	1	60
HUMAN FACTORS ENGINEERING	40	27	7	5	48	13	140
INTEGRATION	29	10	9	4	34	14	100
NUMBER OF PROGRAMS IN DATABASE	64	86	32	21	82	74	359

NOTE: Each technology can impact more than one domain

Survey Analyses

Survey analyses were conducted by Frank Gentner, Dave Kancler, and Dr. Mona Crissey using matrixed printouts from the Liveware database. Descriptive statistics were used to highlight existence of technologies in various categories and to look for trends. Predictive statistics were not considered appropriate since the total population size is unknown. A sample of the analyses conducted follows.

Survey Participation

Liveware survey participation as of February 3, 1993 is summarized in Table 1. The Training domain has had the greatest number (227) of programs listed. The Manpower and Human Factors Engineering domains have the next largest participation, with 142 and 140 programs, respectively. The lowest participation is in the Safety and Health Hazards domains, but they still have achieved 82 and 60 "hits" respectively. Participation by DoD Service shows the U. S. Army has overtaken the Air Force with 86 and 64 technologies, respectively, while the Navy/Marine Corps grouping has only 32 technologies listed. The showing from Industry is quite good, with 82 technologies listed. One hundred technologies indicated they helped achieve integration in some way, whether with integration of two or more domains, or with vertical integration from a lower level of design to a more aggregate level.

Survey Database

The Liveware survey results were entered in a PC FOCUS database. The database contains the facility of displaying matrix-type (cross-tabulation) printouts of survey variables. The survey database will be made available to the both government and industry, and a catalog of the information about each technology will be published and made available NATO-wide.

RESULTS

Results Continue to Arrive

Liveware survey results can be viewed from many perspectives. The results reported in this paper are of the technologies received as of February, 1993; however, surveys continue to arrive and we will report the numbers received as of the end of March 1993 in the NAECON presentation. Below, we have highlighted preliminary results from several areas of interest.

Participation by Liveware Domain. Survey participation is summarized above for both domain and the Service/Industry category (see Table 1, above).

Technology Type. Technologies were classified as either a *tool* (any model, software package, simulation or wargame employed to examine or describe a system or process), *technique* (systematic procedure, method, or mode of inquiry used to accomplish a specific task), or *database* (organized collection of information developed and maintained to support specific applications and functions). Of the 362 categorized, 221 (60 %) were tools,

Figure 3

92 (26%) were databases, and only 49 (14%) were techniques. (See Table 3.)

Owner Sector. Liveware technologies were categorized by the owner segment (commercial, military, other government). Most technologies registered were government owned (military 189 [54%]) and other government, 53 [15] for a total of 69 percent government owned, while 25 percent were owned commercially. (See Figure 4.) Although many contractors completed Liveware surveys (82 or 23% of surveys completed), only 15 percent of the tools were owned by the private sector. Thus, it appears that many of the contractors completing surveys are developing their tools for the government.

Figure 4

Systems Addressed. All system types were addressed, ranging from low of 108 supporting personal equipment to a high of 150 for aircraft. (See Figure 5 for a comparison.)

Figure 5

Mission Area. The missions addressed by Liveware technologies covered all land, sea, air, and Command, Control, Communications and Intelligence (C3I) areas. Coverage ranged from 148 C3I "hits" to 216 for Land missions (see Figure 6). (Since technolo-

gies can cover multiple areas these numbers do not add to 100 percent.)

Figure 6

Technologies Involving Integration. Over 100 technologies involved integration, vertical and horizontal. *Vertical Integration* was defined as taking information from more than one organizational level or development phase and merging it into the program data. *Horizontal integration* was defined as taking information from more than one Liveware domain and merging it with data from another. Of the over 100 technologies which perform some kind of integration, 73 indicated they accomplished vertical integration, 72 horizontal integration, and 49 Technologies accomplished both types of integration(see figure 7).

Figure 7

Development Status. Most (74%) of the technologies are operational, or at least have some finished portion that is available. This statistic helps correct the misperception that HSI tools are "never completed" (see Figure 8).

Figure 8

Acquisition Phase Supported. Owners were asked to list each phase of the defense acquisition process their technologies could support. One hundred seventy owners indicated their technologies were applicable to "design and development," which roughly equates to the DoD "Engineering and Manufacturing Development" phase. Other phases were supported by a low of 111 (production) to a high of 148 for concept development phases (see Figure 9).

Figure 9

DISCUSSION

Coverage of Liveware Tools

Coverage of the Liveware survey appears quite comprehensive. All Liveware domains are covered by a minimum of at least 60 technologies each. The Army and Air Force were well represented, with 86 and 64 technologies, respectively. The combined Navy and Marine Corps had 32 technologies, fewer than one might

expect. Industry seemed to have a strong showing with 82 technologies. Overall, 359 technologies were listed in the Liveware database as of February 3, 1993. Surveys continue to arrive, however, and we expect to be able to present updated figures at the NAECON presentation.

Missing Technologies

One stated goal of the Liveware survey was to identify missing technologies. The survey indicates that all Liveware domains were covered to some degree by a number of technologies. However, since the total population of technologies is not known, it is impossible to determine the percent depicted in the Liveware survey; therefore, it is difficult to pinpoint missing technologies. The lowest number of surveys returned were in the health hazards and safety areas. However, this does not mean that these areas had the least coverage. One could argue that fewer technologies could effectively cover a domain if they adequately address the issues in each sub-area, though are not represented in the number found in other domains. To answer the missing technologies question, we respond that all areas appear to be covered; however, we are not sure how effective these technologies are in meeting user needs. To answer the latter question of effective coverage will take data and analysis beyond the scope of the present study. This follow-on study could compare user needs with the specific performance of each technology. The present survey did not collect such evaluative data, but the Liveware survey is a good place to start to find what technologies exist and how to find out more about them.

Uses of Liveware Survey Database

Assessment Aid. Survey data, displayed and analyzed using the Liveware database, will help identify existing technology. Where the existing technology appears inadequate to meet user needs, the Liveware database will provide a basis to marshal R&D resources. Information will be shared NATO-wide, making maximum use of existing technology wherever it exists. This could ultimately save HSI technology development costs.

Technology Choice Aid. The Liveware database does not rate or rank individual technologies, nor does it provide descriptive information in great detail. It does provide enough information to the analyst, program manager, or developer to narrow the list of appropriate technologies to those which would be of value for the

particular domain, task, or acquisition phase. By the Liveware database providing a broad range of information in an easily queried summary format, the user can narrow the search for appropriate tools quickly. Because it provides POC information about both developers and users, the pursuit of in-depth information about technologies of interest is easily accomplished.

Secondary Benefits. By making the database available and widely advertised to the acquisition community, the Liveware database should have these positive benefits: it will (1) promote state-of-the-art information sharing; (2) help potential users of HSI technology easily find what they need; (3) encourage the use of HSI tools and databases; (4) help identify available technology and gaps; and (5) help set and substantiate the HSI research agenda.

Examples of Specific Uses. The Liveware database has already been used to answer technology questions. For example, a cost analysis center requested a listing of all Liveware tools with connections to cost data. They plan to scrub their database of cost tools by using the Liveware listings. Also, a DoD safety center requested a listing of Health Hazard tools, since they felt their assortment of tools was insufficient. They used the listing to identify tools developed by other Services and industry that could be tailored to their Service. In a third example, a DoD contractor examined a Liveware listing to identify alternative tools to use in a "tool bag" system that will assist human factors personnel choose the most appropriate tool for various task, workload, and related analyses. Based on a review of the Liveware data and the response from the acquisition community, we believe that the Liveware database will be found useful in even more ways than originally envisioned.

ABOUT THE AUTHORS

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DR. MONA J. CRISSEY is the Liveware Project Manager, currently working for the Army Research Lab's Human Research and Engineering Directorate's STRICOM field element in Orlando. While at the Training and Performance Data Center, she was responsible for the design and development of the Liveware survey and database, and the management of the Footprint database. She holds degrees in Education from the University of Alabama (EdD), University of Kentucky (MA), and SUNY Cortland (BS). She was formerly Manager of Administration and Program Manager for the Saudi Naval Expansion Program at Northrop Services, Inc.

DAVID E. KANCLER is a CSERIAC technical analyst assisting in the Liveware survey. Prior to this, he provided datab gathering and analysis services for the CREW CHIEF human-model project at the Armstrong Lab, Wright-Patterson AFB, Ohio. He recently received his MA in psychology from the University of Dayton, specializing in human factors and experimental design. He also holds a BA in psychology from Ohio University.

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